

APERA-TERA 2025

Cultivating Media Literacy and Information Responsibility among Older Adults: A Three-Year Intergenerational Framework for Inclusive Digital Citizenship

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17486098>

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Nov. 1, 2025

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This project / study is funded by the National Science and Technology Council (NSTC), Taiwan, under Grant No. 114-2410-H-194-098-MY3.

CRED LAB

Critical Research | Ethics | Digital Ontologies

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Research Areas

- adult education
- educational technology (EdTech)
- intergenerational learning (IL)
- 55+ learners
- media literacy
- research integrity
- scholarly publishing ethics
- third-person effect (TPE)
- echo chamber effect (ECE)
- algorithm effect (AE)

Project Background & Motivation

- > As of 2025, Taiwan has officially entered the stage of a super-aged society (20% aged 65+).
- > **The “Gray Digital Divide”**: Financial scams surged in Q4 2024 (NT\$37.2B ≈ US\$1.215B lost); **55+ women were the primary victims** (Ministry of the Interior of Taiwan, 2025).
- > **Psychosocial Vulnerability**: Such scams are designed to target **cognitive biases, tech unfamiliarity**, and a high level of trust in authority and peer networks.
- > **Local Context (Southern Taiwan)**: Local lifelong learning institutions face unique challenges, e.g., the **shortage** of qualified media literacy instructors and the **highly diverse** learning needs, styles, and preferences of older learners.

Reference: Ministry of the Interior of Taiwan (2025, Jan 16). *Analysis of high-value fraud financial loss trends in Q4 2024: 3% of fraud cases account for over 57% of financial losses! The Ministry of the Interior urges the public to be cautious with investments to avoid being scammed* [Press release]. https://www.moi.gov.tw/News_Content.aspx?n=2&s=324961.

Research Gaps (Motivation) & Social Relevance

- **Gap 1 (Skills vs. Social Structure):** Current instruction too focuses on skills (e.g., edit photos), **ignoring social and structural risks** (e.g., psychological and algorithmic bias).
- **Gap 2 (Literacy vs. Accountability):** Past studies **overlooked the accountability for online behavior**, including the ethical, legal, and social consequences of sharing misinformation.
- **Gap 3 (Lack Practical Model):** Missing instructional models that integrate older individuals' **cognitive biases** with their socio-technical environments.
- **Goal of the Project:** To empower local 55+ adults to become ethical and responsible social media practitioners, rather than passive and vulnerable users.

Theoretical Framework & Key Concepts

- **Information Responsibility Literacy Indicator for Taiwanese Elder Adults” (IRLI-TEA):** The core construct, moving beyond skills to encompass ethical engagement, and **social and critical awareness** of algorithmic influence.
- **Echo Chamber Effect (ECE):** The mechanisms of social filtering that generate homogeneous information bubbles that **reinforce existing beliefs** and amplify polarization.
- **Third-Person Effect (TPE):** A **cognitive bias** where individuals believe that negative media (e.g., fake news) affects “others” more than “themselves,” thereby lowering personal vigilance and responsibility.
- **Intergenerational Co-Learning:** The **primary intervention** strategy of the project. Facilitates task-based collaboration between age groups to bridge digital and value divides, fostering reciprocal learning and shared understanding.

Research Aims & Key Questions

Aim

To develop and validate the “**Information Responsibility Literacy Indicator for Taiwanese Elder Adults**” (IRLI-TEA), and to design a corresponding modular, hybrid, and intergenerational eLearning curriculum grounded in media literacy.

QRs

- RQ1** How do the **Echo Chamber Effect (ECE)** and **Third-Person Effect (TPE)** shape the (a) information judgment, (b) decision-making processes, and (c) information-sharing behaviors of local adults aged 55+ in online contexts?
- RQ2** What are the **core competencies and structural dimensions** of information responsibility literacy among this demographic?
- RQ3** **In what ways** can a modular media literacy-based eLearning curriculum be designed and implemented to cultivate information responsibility literacy among 55+ adults effectively?

Overview of the 3-Year Mixed-Methods Research

Scope & Collaborators

- A 3-year mixed-methods study
- From Aug. 2025 – Jul. 2028
- Funded by the NSTC of Taiwan
- The CREDO LAB, CCU students (18+)
- 55+ living in southern Taiwan
- **International collaborators (see next page)**

Main Methods

- Y1: Egocentric Network Interviews
- Y2: Focus Groups & Delphi Method
- Y2: Design-Based Research (DBR) Method
- Y3: Quasi-Experimental Field Testing

Collaborators

- Y1: Qualitative Exploration
- Y1: IRLI-TEA Indicator Scoping
- Y2: IRLI-TEA Indicator Construction
- Y2: Curriculum Prototyping
- Y3: Curriculum Implementation
- Y3: Quasi-Experimental Validation

Expected Outputs

- **IRLI-TEA Indicator (openly available)**
- A modular hybrid media literacy curriculum
- **Open educational resources (CC license)**
- Community workshops and exhibitions
- **Journal articles (indexed in SSCI, SCIE)**

Call for Partners (International)

(Y1–Y3) Methodology Research Partners & Global Research Networks: Co-design international studies applying egocentric social network analysis, design-based research (DBR), and quasi-experimental approaches in community-based learning contexts.

(Y2–Y3) Theoretical Collaboration & Global Research Exchange: Engage in joint theoretical development on information responsibility, digital citizenship, and intergenerational learning, aiming to **refine and validate the IRLI-TEA framework across diverse cultural contexts.**

(Y2–Y3) Comparative Studies (International): Conduct cross-cultural comparative research on cognitive biases (ECE/TPE) and media literacy practices among middle-aged and older adults worldwide.

Call for Partners (Domestic)

(Y1–Y2) Experts: Join the **Delphi validation panel** on adult education and media literacy to co-develop robust IRLI-TEA Indicators that inform curriculum and assessment design.

(Y2–Y3) Practitioners: Partner with local lifelong learning institutions, community universities, and Digital Opportunity Centers (DOCs) to **pilot and implement the developed curriculum modules**.

(Y3) Policy Makers: Collaborate with local education and social affairs bureaus to **translate research findings into actionable policy recommendations** and community strategies.

Innovation & Interdisciplinary Value

- **The Conceptual Innovation:** One of the first studies to connect the ECE/TPE with 55+'s media literacy, moving beyond a focus on digital skills to include ethical and cognitive dimensions.
- **Methodological Innovation:** Combines qualitative egocentric network mapping and in-depth interviews with quantitative Delphi validation to construct the IRLI-TEA Indicators for 55+ empirically.
- **Practical Innovation:** Develops a scalable, modular, hybrid, and intergenerational curriculum that leverages modern collaborative tools (e.g., GenAI(s), Gather, Padlet, Kahoot!, chatbot simulators).
- **Interdisciplinary Integration:** Bridges Adult Education, Information Science, Communication Studies, and Social Psychology, creating a cross-field framework for digital literacy research.

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Thank you for your attention!

Let's connect if you're interested in collaborating on this project.

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